

The Ideology of Donald Trump and Joe Biden in Their Political Speeches through Appraisal of Attitude

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ABSTRACT

The title of this study, which is *The Ideology of Donald Trump and Joe Biden in Their Political Speeches through Appraisal of Attitude*, reflects the objectives: to define the attitudinal appraisal of the speeches and to define the ideology of the speakers. To come to the purpose, the researcher implicates the appraisal system of attitude theory proposed by Martin and White (2005) and political discourse to analyze the speakers' ideology. The campaign speech scripts taken from the website www.rev.com were the speech delivered on the same day by the speakers in different places. Therefore, this study applies purposive sampling data with the model of research: qualitative descriptive. The data results show different number, however, the same pattern of attitude used by Donald Trump and Joe Biden. 63% of the data found indicates positive in Donald Trump's campaign speech with the sub-system mostly in use is judgment and a total of 250 items in use. Joe Biden's campaign speech has 65% indicates the use of positive attitude systems and has judgment with the number of items in use: 121 items. Thus, it differs in the way they use attitude to appraise what and how. As well as their social beliefs, since Donald Trump is a part of the Republican and Joe Biden is a Democrat. Accordingly, the use of attitude in their campaign speech and their social beliefs describe them as presidential candidates who will lead America.

KATA KUNCI

penilaian; sikap;
ideologi; wacana
politik; pidato
politik

ABSTRAK

Judul dari penelitian ini adalah The Ideology of Donald Trump and Joe Biden in Their Political Speeches through Appraisal of Attitude, yang mencerminkan tujuan penelitian: untuk mendefinisikan sikap sebagai bagian dari sistem penilaian yang digunakan dalam pidato kampanye, dan untuk mendefinisikan ideologi pembicara. Untuk mencapai tujuan tersebut, peneliti mengimplikasikan teori penilaian yang dikemukakan oleh Martin dan White (2005) dan wacana politik untuk menganalisis ideologi pembicara. Naskah pidato kampanye yang diambil dari website www.rev.com merupakan pidato kampanye yang disampaikan di hari yang sama namun berbeda lokasi oleh kedua kandidat. Penelitian ini menggunakan teknik pengambilan data secara purposive sampling dengan model penelitian deskriptif kualitatif. Hasil data menunjukkan angka yang berbeda, namun pola penilaian sikap yang sama yang digunakan oleh Donald Trump dan Joe Biden. 63% data yang ditemukan merujuk kepada penilaian sikap secara positif dalam pidato kampanye Donald Trump dengan sub sistem yang paling banyak digunakan adalah judgment sebanyak 250 item. 65% dari analisis pada pidato kampanye Joe Biden menunjukkan penggunaan sistem penilaian sikap positif dan paling banyak ditemukan penggunaan judgment, dengan jumlah item yang digunakan: 121 item. Di antara kedua kandidat, yang membedakan penggunaan penilaian sikap dalam pidato kampanye mereka adalah siapa atau apa yang mereka evaluasi dan bagaimana; cara mereka

menilainya. Terkait ideologi mereka sebagai anggota dari partai politik tertentu, sebagaimana Donald Trump adalah bagian dari Republik dan Joe Biden adalah seorang Demokrat, hal tersebut mempengaruhi ideologi mereka dalam hal strategi pemerintahan yang akan mereka jalankan sebagai calon presiden yang akan memimpin Amerika.

INTRODUCTION

The center of Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) is being a model that is multiperspectival for the analysts to interpret the language in use by using its complementary lenses (J. R. Martin & White, 2005, p. 7). These complementarities are the basis to the notion kinds of meaning: ideational, interpersonal and textual meaning, mapped by the language as a resource (J. R. Martin & White, 2005, p. 7). Diving further to each notion of meaning, textual meanings deal with the flow of information. It concerns the distribution of the other two meanings in waves of semiosis as it connects the relation of ideational and interpersonal. Ideational resources deal with interpreting experience. In other words, ideational resources are used to see the relation between what's happening, who's involved, and also why, when, where, how does something happen (J. R. Martin & White, 2005, p. 7). Interpersonal resources deal with negotiating social relations. The way people interact, the feelings they share are concerns in interpersonal resources.

SFL itself, placed in the first level of abstraction from the realization lens the idea of three cycles of coding involved in a stratified semiotic system in a language. The second level is lexicogrammar that deals with phonological and graphological patterns, then followed by discourse semantics which concerned with meaning beyond the clause (J. R. Martin & White, 2005, pp. 8–9). Situated in the level of discourse semantics and constituted a system of interpersonal meanings, appraisal allows dispersion of meanings in the former level and different types of lexicogrammatical systems (Oteiza, 2017, p. 458). White & Martin (2005, p. 42) in the book 'The Language of Evaluation', outlined that the attitude framework deals with mapping feelings. They also divided appraisal into three items: attitude, engagement, and graduation.

The advancement of appraisal can be seen through previous studies, as it has been used by many researchers, especially in the linguistics field. For example, Ertayas (2011) took the three items of appraisal I to analyze gossip texts taken from Perez Hilton.com and to find the ideology of it. Chaerunnisah (2020) only focused on one appraisal system of attitude used in the beauty video bloggers' videos to find the relation between persuasion contained and beauty standards. A different appraisal system, engagement, was used by Respati & Setyaningsih (2011) as the objective of the study to investigate the realization of Barack Obama's power in his speech. Another study in the form of a journal had the same purpose, entitled: Power of Sakdiyah Ma'Ruf in Stand-Up Comedy through appraisal approach. Fatmawati et al. (2018) observed the power of Sakdiyah Ma'Ruf in her stand-up comedy by analyzing the attitudinal appraisal. Another item of the appraisal system, graduation items, was used by C. Fan (2020) to analyze news reports from China Daily and to reveal the ideology of it. J. Sutomo (2014) took the appraisal theory from Martin and White (2005) to analyze the speech of Jokowi at the APEC CEO Summit on 10 November 2014 in Beijing, China. He analyzed it using all of the Appraisal systems, which are attitude, engagement, and graduation. His study got the conclusion that attitude is the most used Appraisal system in the speech of Jokowi. Sangka (2017) took only one of the appraisal systems as the focus of his study. His research identified both positive and negative attitude devices in Michelle Obama's speech towards the presidential candidates in 2016. As can be seen from the previous studies mentioned above, appraisal systems make clear either the power of the speaker towards the audiences or the ideology the speakers try to tell through his speech.

Not only each appraisal item but also the whole appraisal systems are intriguing topics to be learned. From all of the previous studies mentioned above, the researcher decided to choose one appraisal system and

one purpose as the objectives of this study. However, according to Martin and White (2005), the center of the appraisal framework is the attitude system. It has to do with resources to interpret people's feelings as well as the judgment of behavior, emotional reactions, and evaluation of things (J. R. Martin & White, 2005, p. 35). With this capability, attitude can be analyzed in various data, whether in the written or spoken form, whether in a political context or even stand-up comedy.

Recently, the euphoria of the United States of America's presidential election has been experienced not only by Americans but also by people outside America. As a majority and influential country, even the result of the election waited by people around the world. For the new presidential candidates, Donald Trump and Joe Biden stand against each other. Both of them have a significant position in the politics of America. Donald Trump is the incumbent President of America, while Joe Biden was a vice president during the 2009-2017 periods and also has been around America's politics a lot. Seeing how powerful these two candidates, it is interesting to see how they express themselves and convince the people of America to choose them for the next President. During the campaign period, the two of them have been around, giving their campaign speech and telling people their vision, ideology, and strategy in leading the United States of America.

As briefly explained above, the purpose of this study is to see the ideology of Donald Trump and Joe Biden in their political speeches, specifically in their campaign speech during the campaign period. This study uses the appraisal system of attitude theory proposed by Martin and White in 2005 to analyze and to see the difference between Donald Trump and Joe Biden in delivering their campaign speech as a presidential candidate.

METHOD

Research Design

This study applies descriptive qualitative research method with the goal to develop understandings of the attitudinal appraisal pattern in the political speeches of Donald Trump and Joe Biden. This research also works under the appraisal framework and sets the goal to answer the question of how the ideology of the speakers can be seen by analyzing the attitude used in their political speeches. This goes along with the purpose of descriptive research as stated by Gall & Borg (2007), which is more into explaining the 'what' than the 'why' or how' (Nassaji, 2015, p. 129) occurred from the use of attitude in the campaign speech of Donald Trump and Joe Biden.

Source of Data

The data taken for this study is the political speeches of Donald Trump and Joe Biden in their campaign event during the campaign period for America's presidential election. The campaign speeches were delivered by them on the same day which was on 30th September 2020. Joe Biden delivered his speech in front of the people of Johnstown, Pennsylvania while Donald Trump delivered his speech in his campaign event at Duluth, Minnesota. The link for Joe Biden's campaign speech transcript can be accessed on <https://www.rev.com/blog/transcripts/joe-biden-train-tour-campaign-speech-transcript-johnstown-pa-september-30-night-after-debate>, while Donald Trump's campaign speech transcript can be accessed on <https://www.rev.com/blog/transcripts/donald-trump-duluth-minnesota-campaign-rally-transcript-september-30-night-after-first-debate>. Both of the campaign speech transcripts of the two 2020 American's presidential candidates was downloaded by the researcher on January 9th, 2021.

Technique of Data Collection

The researcher accessed the website www.rev.com to get the political speeches of Donald Trump and Joe Biden. Then, selected the political speeches of Donald Trump and Joe Biden delivered only on the campaign event for America's 2020 presidential election. The political campaign speeches of Donald Trump and Joe Biden sorted to the speeches that were delivered on the same day so their ideology can correlate from their speeches. The researcher downloaded the chosen speech transcript of both Donald Trump and Joe Biden to make it easier to do the data analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part provides the difference between the speakers, Donald Trump and Joe Biden, in using the attitude systems in their campaign speech will be revealed and explained. Some examples from the scripts will be provided to support the explanation. After explaining the difference between the uses of each attitudesystem in the speakers' speeches, the ideology of both speakers will also be defined by seeing how they use the overall attitude systems.

Table 1 Result of Data Analysis

No.	Speaker	+/-	Affect	Judgment	Appreciation	Total (Σ)	Total (%)
1.	Donald Trump	+	107	136	114	357	63,0
		-	35	114	61	210	37,0
		Total (Σ)	142	250	175	567	100
	Total (%)	25,0	44,1	30,9	100		
2.	Joe Biden	+	26	74	34	134	65,0
		-	11	47	14	72	35,0
		Total (Σ)	37	121	48	206	100
	Total (%)	18,0	58,7	23,3	100		

Both Donald Trump and Joe Biden have the attitudinal appraisal system of judgment as the most item they use in their campaign speech. Donald Trump's campaign speech has 44,1% of judgment while Joe Biden's campaign speech has a little bit more with the percentage of 58,7%. They only have a slight difference in the number percentage of positive attitudes in their campaign speech, which Donald Trump has 63% and Joe Biden has 65%. Their pattern of use shows approximately the same, as they also have appreciation placed as the second most used item and affect as the least used item. In his campaign speech, Donald Trump used 175 (30,9%) item of appreciation and 142 (25%) item of affect. Joe Biden on the other side, 23,3% of his campaign speech indicated appreciation item with the frequency 48 items were found. There are also 38 (18%) items indicated affect in his campaign speech. The fact that both Donald Trump and Joe Biden used mostly the item of judgment has to do with the purpose of their campaign speech. In order to be as persuasive as possible, they took the advantage of using item of judgment, mostly positively to evaluate themselves in terms of behavior and their characteristic as leaders. While in the negative use, Donald Trump and Joe Biden used it to overtop one another as they evaluate each other often negatively. This way, the audiences could see the upsides of choosing them more clearly since the downsides of the opponent are provided by the use of negative judgment.

In terms of the overall number of attitude found, Donald Trump has more number in his data findings as he tends to spend a longer time than Joe Biden in delivering his speech. In the data taken for this study, he

spent an hour speech while Joe Biden was just had 40 minutes of speech. Thus, it affects the ideology of him as an individual from the perspective that Donald Trump has more items to appraise as he talked about various topics.

Affect

1. Positive Affect

The use of positive affect in the campaign speech of Donald Trump can be seen in the examples below:

(1) Hello, everybody. Hello, Duluth. Hello, Duluth. **Thank you**. (DT/1/AF/+)

Example number (1) is the example where the speaker uses the positive affect of happiness in his campaign speech. The expression 'thank you' indicates the speaker's form of happiness and gratitude toward the audience. Donald Trump has Duluth as one of the cities where he has more supporters than Joe Biden, which is why he had his rally there. Donald Trump did not mention which part of the Duluth has his gratitude since it could be either the people or the city itself. However, since he said it in the beginning and was a part of greetings, it makes sense to say that he was referring to the people of Duluth who were there to listen to his campaign speech. In this sense, the appraised item in example number (1) is the people of Duluth.

(2) Biden will turn Minnesota into a refugee camp. And he **said** that.

The word 'said' in example number (2) indicates a positive form of affect: security. The speaker used the item of security since he was feeling assured about the statement he was about to tell the audience. This way, the information itself is the appraised item. Here, Donald Trump told his audiences about what his rival will do, and to make it assured, he reported it by saying that Joe Biden said that by himself. Therefore, Donald Trump 'guaranteed' what he said is credible by stated 'he said that'. This way, Donald Trump expressed his security towards the information by bringing up Joe Biden into the situation. Donald Trump left the impression that the audiences can trust the statement since he assured them by stating that Joe Biden told that himself.

(3) I **really enjoyed** last night's debate with Sleepy Joe. (DT/4/AF/+)

In example number (3), the phrase 'really enjoyed' refers to the use of positive affect of satisfaction made by Donald Trump towards the debate he had last night. This way, the appraised item is the debate. Donald Trump expressed his feeling towards the presidential candidates' debate he had last night before the rally. He probably felt satisfied by saying he really enjoyed attending the presidential debate he had with his only rival, Joe Biden. Donald Trump even added the word 'really' to show that he was at the point where it can be said that he was impressed. He did not mention which part of the debate he enjoyed, since it can be either his debating opponent, his performance while debating, or the debate event itself. Donald Trump only showed his satisfaction about the debate by saying he 'really enjoyed' the debate, then stating that he was doing it with Joe Biden. Here it can probably be said that the closest possibility about the thing he enjoyed the most from the debate is the debating process with Joe Biden.

(4) I **hope** your US attorney is involved. What is going on with Omar? (DT/240/AF/+)

In example number (4), Donald Trump shows his positive affect of inclination by using the word 'hope'. He brought up Omar in the speech and revealed the things she did, including what he called 'harvesting'. The term harvesting in politics means a practice where political operatives drop collect absentee ballots off at a polling place or election office after collecting them from voters' homes. As a politician, this is for sure not

the right thing to do. The people chose her while she abused their votes. Ballots harvesting counts as a form of corruptible practice, and in some cases it even causes reelection. Due to this, Donald Trump expressed his feeling by hoping that Omar has a US attorney to save her. The word 'hope' itself refers to instead of reacting to Omar caught harvesting emotionally, Donald Trump intended that Omar should have her US attorney involved as she has been caught and there will be action taken. Then, the appraised item in example number (4) is Omar.

Onto the next speaker, the use of positive Affect in the campaign speech of Joe Biden can be seen in the examples below:

(5) Love Johnstown. (JB/1/AF/+)

Example number (5) has the word 'love', which indicates the item of happiness. Joe Biden delivered his campaign speech in front of the people of Johnstown. He started with greeted them, along with expressing his feeling towards the audiences. He got the chance to tell his campaign speech at Johnstown with no other reason than the fact that he had more votes there than his rival. As a presidential candidate, holding a winning state is crucial even in the campaign period, since it can help predict the winning possibility. Here, Joe Biden directly expressed that he had a positive feeling towards his audiences, the people of Johnstown. As the people of Johnstown supported him and they also came to hear his campaign speech, Joe Biden used the word 'love' to let his audiences knew that he liked them as his supporters. Therefore, the appraised item in this example is the audience.

(6) He said it'd be gone by Easter. (JB/88/AF/+)

The word 'said' used by Joe Biden in example number (6) refers to as an item of security. Joe Biden also referred to Donald Trump as the owner of the information. As the incumbent President of the United States, Donald Trump had an extra duty to protect the people of America from the global pandemic COVID-19 that occurred lately. The global pandemic has prevented people to do normal activities and it affected a lot of aspects including the economic cycle. Therefore, not only in America, everyone asked for answers for when it will over. Joe Biden revealed that as the head of America, Donald Trump, rather than giving out a sensible answer, he just stated that it would be gone when the weather is warm. Of course, Joe Biden gave out this statement to give the impression to his audience about how irresponsible Donald Trump is as a president and presidential candidate. Joe Biden used the word 'said' to make it seems like Donald Trump's statement did come from him while Joe Biden just reported it to his audiences. Also, Joe Biden relied upon Donald Trump for the credibility of the information.

(7) It's good to be back. (JB/2/AF/+)

In example number (7) and in other statements of Joe Biden that also use the item of satisfaction, the referred word is 'good'. As stated at the beginning of the speech as a part of greetings, Joe Biden expressed his positive feelings towards Johnstown. Joe Biden said that the last time he was in Johnstown, the city was all Democrat. Joe Biden himself is a part of Democrat, which is why he had such a positive feeling. His feeling of satisfaction referred to the fact which he decided 'to be back'. The fact that Johnstown is still a Democrat by the time Joe Biden came for his campaign grabbed him. As a Democrat, it is for sure an achievement to keep a city still being Democrat even after a different period. Here, the loyalty of people in Johnstown is why Joe Biden came back there. The feeling of 'coming back' to the place where there are still people who support him was what got Joe Biden impressed. The appraised item in this example is Johnstown, specifically the feeling it gave to Joe Biden as the speaker, which he considered as 'being back'.

(8) I want to thank the lieutenant governor, for being here. (JB/13/AF/+)

The word 'want' in example number (8) indicates the affect item of inclination that appraised the lieutenant governor. Joe Biden expressed his positive feelings not only towards his audiences but also the people around him. Some of the city's politicians also stand on his side to support Joe Biden to win the election and become the next president. In his campaign speech at Johnstown, one of the people he mentioned was Johnstown's lieutenant governor. Fortunately, the governor was also there to show his support directly to Joe Biden. Therefore, Joe Biden stated that he appreciated his time to come and intended to thank him. Before giving out the statement where he thanking the lieutenant governor, Joe Biden stated his intention prior which is why the item of inclination is indicated in this example.

2. Negative Affect

The following examples are the examples where Donald Trump applies negative affect:

(9) Liberal media is upset that I took the fight to Biden and exposed his very dangerous agenda. (DT/43/AF/-)

In example number (9), the word 'upset' indicates unhappiness. The appraised item is the action that Donald Trump took. The appraiser is who Donald Trump referred to as 'liberal media'. It leaves the impression that the liberal media was on the side of Joe Biden while the term 'liberal' itself is not a proper reference. By saying such thing, it leaves the impression that Donald Trump let the people know what Joe Biden was trying to do while the one who feels unhappy about the situation is the liberal media. This way, the audiences would feel betrayed as Joe Biden teamed up with the liberal media to do things behind their back. However, since Donald Trump reported that the liberal media react to his action negatively, the audience would think that Joe Biden and liberal media somehow did team-up.

(10) I was getting worried. (DT/96/AF/-)

The phrase 'was getting worried' in example number (10) indicates the item of insecurity. The appraiser is Donald Trump, which he implicitly appraised the city of Texas. Donald Trump revealed that Texas has some of the greatest people there. Donald Trump was mentioning the city-state that supports law enforcement when he also mentioned Antifa. Texas is the city Donald Trump mentioned as a city that stands by him as pro-law enforcement and a city with great people. However, their authority was probably taken by the Antifa, which he referred to as a domestic terrorist organization. Donald Trump expressed he was feeling uneasy about Texas being attacked, but he believed the people of Texas could handle it.

(11) So, disappointed in Fox. (DT/58/AF/-)

In example number (11), Donald Trump expressed his dissatisfaction towards Fox by using the word 'disappointed'. He explicitly revealed his feelings toward the media negatively. He mentioned some of the liberal media that did nothing but supporting the riots. Donald Trump is a part of Republican so that is why he is so against a Democrat. He stated that they killed the living inside the country. Donald Trump also said that those media that stand with his rival are probably either corrupt far-left media or apart of the Democrat party. Fox was one of the media that was not supporting Donald Trump when he fought against Joe Biden, and that leads to the reason why Donald Trump had such negative feelings. He thought Fox was more displeasing to him as the media sort of did not care about riot or Arson but they could let Donald Trump do nothing to expose Joe Biden.

(12) And the press doesn't want to talk about it. (DT/148/AF/-)

Example number (12) has the phrase 'doesn't want' which refers to an item of disinclination. Donald Trump talked about America's energy resources and their relation to national security and economic security. Donald Trump stated The Bidens robbed American workers and mistreated them for money. The media

either did not know which side has the right statement or they already decided not to choose any side. Even so, refusing one party would also lead to the speculation that they could be on the other party since there were only two presidential candidates. Despite the reasons that might be truth behind it, the media chose not to talk about it as Donald Trump stated their disinclination clearly.

The following examples are the use of negative affect made by Joe Biden in his campaign speech:

(13) Maybe that's why he doesn't like me very much. (JB/117/AF/-)

Here, the appraised item is Joe Biden, while the appraiser is Donald Trump that Joe Biden referred to with 'he'. The phrase 'doesn't like' indicates an expression of unhappiness. Joe Biden assumed that Donald Trump probably has a negative feeling towards him since he was interested in stock portfolios while Joe Biden has none. The negative feeling of Donald Trump assumed by Joe Biden from the fact that they have nothing in common, including their interest.

(14) Maybe we're going to have to worry about whether or not they're turning the electricity off because we're behind on our bill because of job change or I lost my health insurance. (JB/51/AF/-)

In example number (14) the word 'worry' indicates insecurity. Joe Biden was telling a story about his life before becoming a politician, as a middle-class person. One of the struggles that had been an everyday topic of conversation is their economic state that sometimes unstable. It even could be on the state where they feel restless about their electricity bill unpaid and would live in the dark sometimes. In this example, Joe Biden referred to him along with his audiences since a lot of his audiences were middle-class people. His audiences would probably relate to this kind of situation where they feel restless towards their unstable situation in life. Therefore, the appraised item is the situation which in this example Joe Biden mentioned as being cut from using the electricity as the effect of losing a job or losing health insurance.

(15) Oh, man. (JB/12/AF/-)

The first negative affect of dissatisfaction item realization is realized in example number (15). Here, Joe Biden reacted to his audience's question about the presidential candidates' debate he attended the night before the rally. Joe Biden responded with the expression 'Oh, man.' which implicitly tells his feeling of dissatisfaction. The debate event did not bring pleasure to him, so he reacted that way. His responses can be considered straight as dissatisfaction as he made it noticeable from his intonation and facial expression. Since it was his response to the question related to the presidential candidates' debate, the appraised item is the debate then.

Judgment

1. Positive Judgment

In the campaign speech of Donald Trump, he used positive judgment with the frequency 136 times. The following examples are some of them:

(16) They used to talk about it every day, "He's not going to get his financing." (DT/73/JD/+)

In example number (16), the expression 'used to talk about it every day' refers to positive normality. The use of the word 'every day' also makes it more noticeable as it is something that they usually did. The appraised item that the speaker referred to as 'it' in his statement is a wall. Donald Trump talked about the wall on the southern border that was already 350 miles far. The wall was supposed to be a fence between

America and Mexico. He also said Mexico paid for it while some of the news fact-checked it and found out that Mexico was not paid for it. People assumed Donald Trump would not get his financing for building the wall. However, he sort of bragged about being a real-estate developer makes everything easy, then he and his people got their financing. Suddenly, people stopped talking about the walls. Donald Trump himself felt it as he stated that people use to have it as everyday conversation.

(17) You can do whatever you want. (DT/48/JD/+)

The modality ability and capacity ‘can’ in example number (17) relates to judgment item of capacity. Donald Trump sarcastically judged the mindset of media outlets such as CNN and The New York Times. These media outlets, as told by Donald Trump, did not care about riots. In this example, Donald Trump talked as if he was in the perspective of the media outlets and evaluate the capacity of rioters.

(18) I will defend our borders. (DT/70/JD/+)

In example number (18), the modality ‘will’ indicates Judgments of tenacity. Donald Trump appraises himself as a presidential candidate to defend the borders of America. He compared himself to his rival and promised his audience to protect the nation’s borders. He meant his promise as later he revealed his project of building a wall on the southern border as a fence between the United States and Mexico.

(19) The whole nation saw the truth. (DT/26/JD/+)

In example number (19), Donald Trump uses the expression ‘saw the truth’ to appraise the whole nation. Donald Trump talked about last night’s debate where he asked Joe Biden to mention one city that supports law enforcement along with him. Donald Trump is known as a proud Republican and also someone that is into law enforcement. He revealed he got so many endorsements from law enforcement organizations. Joe Biden was not someone that fully support law enforcement so when Donald Trump asked such a question, he chose not to answer. The presidential candidates’ debate broadcasted across the country so people can see that moment.

(20) Look at this crowd, this was supposed to be a few people. (DT/321/JD/+)

In example number (20), the modality ‘supposed’ indicates a judgment of propriety. Donald Trump used it to evaluate his campaign event. He expected a small number of people to come to hear his campaign speech when in realization, a whole crowd was there. It was also because during the campaign, the pandemic was a thing, and gather around in groups was highly prohibited. However, people kept coming to hear Donald Trump’s campaign speech while wearing masks for health protocol.

Joe Biden on the other side applies 74 items of positive judgment in his campaign speech. The realizations are as applied in the following examples:

(21) It meant I always remembered what and who really mattered in my life. (JB/37/JD/+)

In example number (21) Joe Biden as the speaker appraises himself for keep on remembering those who mattered in his life. The word ‘always’ refers to a behavior that is constantly done by Joe Biden. He said that he sacrificed his energy to go back and forth to his home by train just to be with his family every day. He actually rode that train every single day before, which intended that it had become his habit. In this example, Joe Biden evaluated himself for his habit of taking the train back and forth so that he would be able to be with his family every single day.

(22) By the way, Donald Trump can only see the world from Park Avenue. (JB/114/JD/+)

In example number (22), Joe Biden reported that Donald Trump how he only sees the world from Park Avenue. Joe Biden uses the modality 'can' which refers to Judgments of capacity. He appraised Donald Trump as someone arrogant. Park Avenue is a place that is usually related to money power, as well as the American dream. While to see the world only from Park Avenue, moreover as a President and a presidential candidate, this is not the image he should have. Even though the judgments of capacity made by Joe Biden form positively, the context itself is negative for the image of Donald Trump.

(23) I'm running as a proud Democrat, but I will be an American President. (JB/187/JD/+)

While in example number (23), Joe Biden appraises himself as a decisive person for being the President of America. He mentioned himself as a proud Democrat and if he wins, he is the President for all Americans after all. Democrat or not, he convinced himself as a promising candidate for all of American. In this example, he uses the modality 'will' that belongs to the Judgments of tenacity.

(24) Quite frankly, my whole career. (JB/31/JD/+)

In example number (24), Joe Biden appraises himself by using the adverb 'quite frankly'. It refers to Judgments of veracity where Joe Biden honestly told that the people of Amtrak have been supporting him all the time. He even has the nickname 'Amtrak Joe' for him always rode the Amtrak train to go to work in Washington D.C. and also to go back home in Delaware. He chose to take the train every day after a traumatic car accident that made him lost his wife and daughter. After that accident, Amtrak is his primary mode of transportation that takes him to work and home.

(25) I think you're supposed to earn money while you're in politics. (JB/121/JD/+)

While in example number (25), Joe Biden evaluates politicians in general. He used the modality 'supposed' to refer to Judgment of propriety. Joe Biden came from a middle-class level family even before big, he was a middle-class person. He also did not think to be a politician means having more money than other people. He was even listed as the poorest man in Congress. However, it was because he did not think to be a politician means being a money collector.

2. Negative Judgment

The examples below are the use of negative Judgment in the campaign speech of Donald Trump:

(26) They don't talk about the wall anymore, fellas. (DT/71/JD/-)

In example number (64), Donald Trump evaluates the 'they' in his statement using the phrase 'don't talk about the wall anymore'. Donald Trump spoke about his project to build a fence wall between the United States and Mexico on the southern border. He revealed that people normally talked about it since it pulled so many speculations whether about the financing or which country that actually paid for the construction. However, since the day Donald Trump got his financing for doing the wall construction, people talked about it no more.

(27) Joe Biden is too weak to lead this country. (DT/28/JD/-)

Donald Trump used the adjective ‘too weak’ to evaluate Joe Biden in example number (27). He used the adjective that refers to negative judgment of capacity. Donald Trump told his audiences that he felt like debating two people when he was doing the presidential candidate’s debate last night. The moderator prevented Donald Trump to ask controversial things related to law enforcement to Joe Biden. Therefore Donald Trump felt offended. He straight up stated that Joe Biden has no capability in leading the country since in the debate last night, even the moderator saved him many times.

(28) I won't bore you, but I could go on and on that. (DT/105/JD/-)

Donald Trump appraised himself in example number (28), where he used the modality ‘will not’. Therefore, the modality indicates negative tenacity as the modality ‘will’ indicates tenacity. Donald Trump mentioned the cities where he has more supporters than Joe Biden. Those cities also support law enforcement, just like him, so that is probably the biggest reason why he has more supporters there. Donald Trump speculated it was so much, until the point where he might get his audiences bored, so he decided not to do that.

(29) I held Joe Biden accountable for his 47 years of lie, 47 years of betrayal, and 47 years of failure. (DT/20/JD/-)

The word ‘lie’ in example number (29) straight up indicates a negative form of veracity. Donald Trump evaluates Joe Biden in being a politician. Donald Trump did not reveal what kind of lies did he means. However, he just stated that he held the accountable of Joe Biden for some of the things, including the lies.

(30) Our opponents stand with rioters. (DT/83/JD/-)

In example number (30), Donald Trump uses the term ‘rioters’ that indicates the use of negative propriety. Rioters refer to the people who move in a crowd to do violent disturbance of the peace. This action is for sure illegal as it against peace. Therefore Donald Trump stated that Joe Biden stands with this kind of people.

While in Joe Biden’s campaign speech, the use of negative judgment can be seen in the examples below:

(31) He's a complete failure. (JB/92/JD/-)

The noun ‘a complete failure’ in example number (31) indicates a negative judgment of capacity. Joe Biden appraised Donald Trump who is no other than his rival. Joe Biden evaluates Donald Trump in terms of his performance as the current President of America. Joe Biden stated Donald Trump failed to take responsibility when the global pandemic occurred and closed many places, including schools and businesses. Joe Biden even judged him as an irresponsible person in being ahead of the country.

(32) Donald Trump will never understand. (JB/164/JD/-)

Joe Biden appraised Donald Trump explicitly in this example. He used the negative form of modality ‘will’ which relates to the Judgment of tenacity. Joe Biden evaluates Donald Trump as a leader, Donald Trump only sees the rich and looks down on the middle to lower-class people. Joe Biden on the opposite promoted himself as a completely different person who will look out more into middle-class people.

(33) He thinks that, if he just yells louder and louder, throws out lie after lie after lie, he'll get his way. (JB/80/JD/-)

In example number (33), the phrase ‘lie after lie after lie’ indicates negative veracity. Joe Biden appraised Donald Trump who kept on giving out lies to the people. Here in this example, Joe Biden exposed Donald

Trump whose keeps on giving false promises to his supporters. Joe Biden also revealed that Donald Trump thought if he keeps on throwing false promises to the people of America, he will get their votes.

(34) They look down the nose at working families trying to do it right. (JB/104/JD/-)

The phrase 'look down the nose' in example number (34) refers to negative propriety. Joe Biden used the phrase to evaluate Donald Trump and his people. To look down at nose means to disrespect people. While having a conversation, looking into someone's eyes means paying attention. In this example as had been stated by Joe Biden, Donald Trump did not care about working people and make it seems like as a leader of the country, he was being biased.

Appreciation

1. Positive Appreciation

Donald Trump has the frequency of 114 items recognized as positive appreciation. Here are some of the examples:

(35) But it turns out big. (DT/163/AP/+)

In example number (35), Donald Trump showed his reaction towards the number of people who came to be his audience as it was beyond his expectation. He thought his campaign event would just be a little get-together with few people and along with a mini celebration since he opened Iron Range back. However, a lot more people showed up at his campaign event so he reacted to it positively.

(36) We've done a good job over there. (DT/211/AP/+)

In example number (36), Donald Trump reviewed the quality of the job he and some of the mayors who he mentioned as a part of Democrats had done. Donald Trump appraised them along with himself for doing such good quality of performance as politicians.

(37) You were one of the most hard hit states for whatever reason. (DT/280/AP/+)

Donald Trump appraised Minnesota, where he delivered his campaign speech, with the adjective 'the most hard' in example number (37). Donald Trump mentioned terrorism and refugee influx when he said that the state of Minnesota somehow got the hit the most. Donald Trump also stated that he did not know the reason behind it either.

(38) These are real warriors. (DT/383/AP/+)

Donald Trump used the adjective 'real' in example number (38) to indicate positive valuation. He valued the people who fight against impeachment hoax that usually attack the holder of a public office.

Moving on to the opponent of Donald Trump, Joe Biden, in his campaign speech applies 34 positive appreciation as can be seen in the examples provided below:

(39) It's been an incredible day. (JB/9/AP/+)

Joe Biden in example number (39) appraised his day and reacted to it as 'incredible'. He was actually sarcastically stating it as he talked about the debate event where he was debating his rival, Donald Trump, afterward.

(40) The man doesn't deserve to be Commander in Chief of the world's best military. (JB/27/AP/+)

In example number (40), Joe Biden appraised the military where Donald Trump was in. Donald Trump was known to be a commander in chief of all Armed Forces of The United States when he became a President. Joe Biden directly reacted to the Armed Forces positively as he said it is the best quality of military in the world.

(41) It was a constant reminder that every single person has their own unique story, their own journey. (JB/60/AP/+)

In example number (41), Joe Biden appraised a reminder that he got from his journey. He appraised it positively since it keeps him reminded of other people for their different life stories, likewise the need to respect them.

(42) It starts with a simple proposition. (JB/166/AP/+)

In example number (42), Joe Biden appraised his proposition as a presidential candidate. He refers to the word 'simple' to indicate it is not as complicated as a political plan might be, so it has higher possibilities to be done and succeeded. The term 'simple' can also mean a straightforward plan that everyone could understand the way it works.

(43) It wasn't Ozzie and Harriet stuff, it was just sort of cornflakes. (JB/34/AP/+)

In example number (43), Joe Biden used the term 'just sort of cornflakes' to value his family positively. He had said that he rode the Amtrak Train every single day. He did that so he could be with his family in the morning before going to work and the night after he finished work. His effort showed how much he valued his family, even just for a simple breakfast instead of a fancy one. However, he still did all of that to show that he considered his family above any other things.

2. Negative Appreciation

Donald Trump's campaign speech has 14 items indicated as negative Appreciation. Here are some of the realizations:

(44) You were one of the most hard hit states for whatever reason. (JB/281/AP/-)

In example number (44), Donald Trump reacted as if the reason why Minnesota being the hardest-hit state of refugee influx did not grab him. It was also the fact that he did not know if there was a specific reason behind it and he seemed not enthusiastic about the perspectives of the people who did it.

(45) I don't get that because the Democrats have done such a lousy pathetic job. (DT/230/AP/-)

Donald Trump used the adjectives 'lousy pathetic' and 'the worst' to refer to negative quality in the examples above. In example number (45), the appraised item is the job of Democrats. He even mentioned it as 'lousy pathetic' which somehow leaves the impression of not only the job is done badly, but also worth looking down on. The use of the adjective is considered a negative reaction regarding the quality of the job that Democrat had done since Donald Trump is a part of Republican, the opposite party of Democrat.

(46) I strongly support the replacement of the decaying Line 3 pipeline. (DT/200/AP/-)

Donald Trump used the adjective 'decaying' to refer to the composition of the Line 3 pipeline. Decaying means the pipe started to have damage and no longer intact. Here, Donald Trump stated that he agreed to do the replacement as the pipeline is already flawed.

(47) A critical issue because they were targeted by China. (DT/160/AP/-)

In example number (47), Donald Trump used the adjective 'critical' to appraise the issue. The adjective refers to negative complexity as Donald Trump made a statement about China targeted the Iron Range. It is indicated as critical issue since if China has it, then America will lose not only natural resources but also jobs due to the fact that a lot of people were involved there. That was also the reason why Donald Trump opened it back, because of the potential of Iron Range.

(48) I think they could have had him for less. (DT/142/AP/-)

In example number (48), Donald Trump directly valued Joe Biden by saying that he only got his job in politics since his dad opened the way and even paid him. Donald Trump negatively valued Joe Biden from his statement that the people who hired Joe Biden could have him 'for less' or in other words, Joe Biden does not value that much for him.

Joe Biden on the other hand, used 8 negative appreciation in his campaign speech and here are some of the examples:

(49) We started this morning in Cleveland, Ohio, where just last night I had a truly unique experience of debating whatever his name was, Donald Trump. (JB/11/AP/-)

In this example, Joe Biden used the expression 'whatever' to indicate even the name of his rival did not grab his attention at all. The use of the word 'whatever' usually represents a careless expression where the speaker did not even have the intention to know. Here, Joe Biden reacted to his rival negatively as he did not interested even in mentioning the name of Donald Trump.

(50) I know this sounds ridiculous. (JB/145/AP/-)

In example number (50), Joe Biden negatively reacted to the plan of his rival to cut Medicaid and the social security from the people of America. He exposed it to convince his audiences that his opponent is no better person with such plans where it will disadvantages the people the most.

(51) I tell you what, I wonder if you're having the same conversation that my mom and dad had when we were growing up, sitting there, wondering, "Honey, we need four new tires on the car. (JB/48/AP/-)

The adjective 'same' in this example is considered negative complexity. The fact is that the context of the conversation that is being appraised by Joe Biden is not in a positive term. Here, the conversation is about how middle-class people talk about their everyday worries regarding their economic situation that is unstable. Middle-class people have this conversation which most of the time contain their worries and questioning so much 'how's is not a good conversation to be having every day. Therefore the adjective 'same' indicates negative complexity since the context is negative.

(52) By the way, if this, if I tried, if we made a movie about this, they'd think it's just all fiction. (JB/132/AP/-)

In example number (117), the expression ‘all fiction’ refers to negative valuation. Joe Biden stated if the situation nowadays turned into a movie, many people would think it is not a- based on a true story-movie. This is not a negative value for movies in general, however, for something that happened in real life where a lot of people died and to value it as fiction can be considered negative valuation.

Ideology

Seeing from the overall use of Attitude, Donald Trump has a significantly bigger number in use as he had a longer campaign speech than Joe Biden. However, their overall use also differs from the perspective that Donald Trump tends to appraise himself and his future plan as a presidential candidate. The campaign speeches of both candidates are taken on the same day of delivery which means they both faced the same issues as it was happening in the United States of America. One of the issues that most unlikely to miss out is the global pandemic. Donald Trump who was the current incumbent President at the moment along with a presidential candidate, barely uses any item of attitude to express or evaluate this issue. Joe Biden was more into the global pandemic issue, as he mentioned it more often than Donald Trump. It is almost impossible not to bring up this topic since the impact is getting everywhere including the economic system. Therefore, the ideology of them as an individual can also be seen in this point of view. The fact that Donald Trump most likely to use the items of attitude to evaluate himself and his strategy in the future reflects that he really took the advantage of the campaign event to promote himself. While Joe Biden, from the way he used Attitude to appraise the current issue happening represents his tactics as a candidate who will fix what had gone wrong and take that as a starter point.

Even if Donald Trump and Joe Biden somehow use the Appraisal system of Attitude in an almost similar way, their use is different. They appraise various things that differ from each other although with the same item, and it shows their own ideology as an individual. Whereas as a part of the social representation of Republicans and Democrats, they have the prevalent ideology that the group member would have while it reflected in the way they set their tactics as a presidential candidate.

CONCLUSION

The use of attitude of Donald Trump and Joe Biden can be relatively conclude as Donald Trump who is more into evaluating himself as a candidate to persuade his audiences to see his potential, while Joe Biden is the candidate who is more into appreciating the people as a way to get the impression that he is the candidate who knew exactly what people want and need. Besides the appraisal system of attitude that can define the speaker's ideology as an individual, their participation in a specific political party can also represent their social beliefs. As a representation of the Republican Party, Donald Trump strictly adhered to the traditional values while establishing his strategy. Joe Biden was more liberal while devoted to fair policies and equal chance for everyone, likewise a member of the Democrat Party.

REFERENCES

- Chaerunnisah, I. U. (2020). *Attitudinal Appraisal in Beauty Vloggers’ Foundation-Related Videos and Its Relation to Persuasion and Beauty Standards*. In Yogyakarta: The Graduate Program in English Language Studies, Sanata Dharma University (Vol. 8, Issue 5). Sanata Dharma University.
- Ertayas, P. C. (2011). *An Appraisal Analysis of Gossip News Texts Written by Perez Hilton from Perez Hilton.com (A Study Based on Systemic Functional Linguistics)*.

Rahmaida, Aulya Puspa & Cahyono, Setyo Prasiyanto. (2022). The Ideology of Donald Trump and Joe Biden in Their Political Speeches through Appraisal of Attitude. *UJARAN (Undergraduate Journal for Academic Research in Humanities)*. 1 (01), 14–29.

Fatmawati, Z. R., Cahyono, S. P., & Cahyono, S. P. (2018). *Power of Sakdiyah Ma'Ruf in Stand-Up Comedy Through Appraisal Approach*. *ETERNAL (English Teaching Journal)*, 9(2), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.26877/eternal.v9i2.2965>

J. Sutomo. (2014). *Appraisal System Recognized in President Jokowi's Speech at the APEC SEO Summit 2014 in Beijing, China*. J. Sutomo FBIB, Universitas Stikubank Semarang. 19–35.

Martin, J. R., & White, P. R. R. (2005). The Language of Evaluation. In *Canadian Journal for Studies in Discourse and Writing/Rédactologie* (Vol. 6, Issue 2). Palgrave Macmillan UK. <https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230511910>

Nassaji, H. (2015). Qualitative and descriptive research: Data type versus data analysis. *Language Teaching Research*, 19(2), 129–132. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168815572747>

Oteíza, T. (2017). The appraisal framework and discourse analysis. In *The Routledge Handbook of Systemic Functional Linguistics*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315413891>

Respati, A. S., & Setyaningsih, N. (2015). *The Realization of Power Through Appraisal System of Engagement of Barack Obama's Victory Speeches*. 2003, 1–15.

Sangka, W. D. (2017). *Appraisal Theory of Attitude in Michelle Obama Speech Towards Presidential Candidates of the United States 2016*. Letters and Humanities Faculty State Islamic University Syarif Hidayatullah